

(zone of inhibition, 11–14 mm), *P. vulgaris* (12–18 mm), *Pseudomonas, SP.* (18–21 mm), *Bacillus* (10–17 mm), *E. coli* (12–17 mm) and *Salmonella* (10–14 mm) by cup-plate method⁶ at a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in DMF by using standard co-trimazine (25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) for bacteria. Amongst the compounds tested for their antibacterial activity, the activity of compounds **3f** and **3g** containing chlorine at *meta*- and *para*-positions showed high activity and other compounds showed good to moderate activity. On *Pseudomonas, SP.*, all compounds showed strong action (18–21 mm) whereas on *Salmonella* all compounds showed poor activity (9–14 mm).

Antifungal activity was tested by cup-plate method⁷ at a concentration of 100 mg ml^{-1} in DMF by using greseofulvin (10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) as standard against *Aspergillus niger* (10–13 mm) and *Fusarium* (9–12 mm). All compounds showed poor activity against the fungi, whereas **3a** was inactive against *A. niger*.

Experimental

The arylthiocarbamides were prepared⁸ by the interaction of appropriate aminemonochloride and ammonium thiocyanate. Tetra-*O*-benzoyl-D-glucopyranosylbromide was prepared⁹ by the interaction of brominating reagent and glucose pentabenzoate. The tetra-*O*-benzoyl-D-glucopyranosylarylisothiocarbamides were prepared⁹ by the interaction of tetra-*O*-benzoyl-D-glucopyranosyl bromide and aryl thiocarbamides. The 2-*S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1-aryl-5-*p*-tolyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets were prepared² by the interaction of *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate and appropriate *S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1-arylisothiocarbamides. Phenyl isocyanodichloride was prepared¹⁰ by passing chlorine gas through the solution of phenyl isothiocyanate in chloroform.

3-Aryl-2-phenylimino-6-*p*-tolylimino-4-*S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-D-glucopyranosyl-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine (hydrochloride) (3a-g): To a clear solution of 2-*S*-tetra-*O*-benzoyl-D-glucopyranosyl-1-*o*-tylyl-5-*p*-tolyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (0.005 mol, 4.46 g) in dry benzene medium (30 ml) was added gradually phenyl isocyanodichloride (0.005 mol, 0.87 g). The resultant mixture after shaking for 10 min was

refluxed on a boiling water-bath for 3.5 h. After heating, benzene was distilled off and the resulting sticky mass was triturated several times with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°). The pale yellow solid (**3b**; 3.8 g, 74%) was crystallized from ethanol-water, m.p. 120° (Found: N, 5.16; S, 6.46. $\text{C}_{57}\text{H}_{47}\text{N}_4\text{O}_9\text{S}_2\text{Cl}$ calcd. for: N, 5.43; S, 6.21%).

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